

**INVESTIGATIONS OF THE COMMUNICATION
SKILLS WITH RESPECT TO DIFFERENT VARIABILITIES
OF SPORT SCIENCES FACULTY STUDENTS:
EXAMPLE OF KOCAELİ UNIVERSITY, TURKEY**

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Abstract:

The purpose of this research is to determine whether the communication skills of Kocaeli University School of Sports Sciences students differ according to some demographic variables. For this purpose, 270 students from the School of Physical Education and Sports at Kocaeli University Sports Sciences Faculty, Coaching Education, Sports Management, Recreation and Physical Education and Sports Teaching Department participated voluntarily. The data were gathered with "Personal Information Form" and "Communication Skills Assessment Scale" (İBDÖ), which was developed by Korkut (1997) to determine communication skills levels of university students which was later validated. İBDÖ is 5 Likert type scales. This form is comprised of 25 articles. SPSS 22 package program was used to analyze the obtained data. In the analysis of the data, T-test and Anova analysis were used. The difference between the variables was interpreted on the basis of p0.05 significance level. As a result of the study, there was found a significant difference between students' communication skills according to their gender and the class they study, and there was not significant difference between communication skills according to their age and the department they studied.

Keywords: communication, communication skills, sports, university student

1. Introduction

In the literature we see that various definitions are made for communication. Communication, Cüceloğlu (2006) defined it as inter-related message exchanges between two units, Johnson and Johnson defines it as to send messages to influence the recipient or the behavior of the recipient; Dökmen (2004) defines it as the processes of

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producing, transmitting and understanding information; Şahin (1997) discusses the importance of communication, as it is the process of transferring feelings, thoughts or information to others in any way that might come to mind, and defines it as the process of creation, association and sharing of meanings between two or more people. If you look at these definitions, you will encounter information transfer as a common point.

Baltas (1992) refers to some features that will improve communication in favor of those who will establish the basis of the agreement and communicate the agreement. These features are listed below, which will facilitate agreement.

- 1) The first minute in communication has a big importance.
- 2) Communication is not a mutual exchange of information.
- 3) Communication is not for the person; it is done with the person.
- 4) Communication is a perfect.

People also need communication, such as sleep, eating, drinking and love, which are basic needs. This is both an individual and a social need. As a social entity, people are aware of the need to communicate. Communication is one of the most important elements necessary for a person to adapt to the environment. Individuals with basic communication skills communicate well with their surroundings. As a process, communication is about sharing action beyond the individual's influence on another. Communication is therefore not a one-way process but a two-way process (Gürgen, H., 1997).

In general, three types of communication are mentioned. These are verbal communication, nonverbal communication and written communication (Topaloğlu, M., 2002). This is the most effective means of communication. Oral communication is also called speech language. Oral Communication is a type of communication which covers face to face interviews, meetings and telephone interviews. It has the advantage of being faster than written communication. Because the receiver does not only hear but also uses the hand and face movements, to interpret the sender's message (Can, H., 1999). The most commonly used form of communication in interpersonal social and cultural settings is verbal communication. Because it is the most effective, fast and face to face communication. Nonverbal communication (body language); it is a communication which is formed of non-verbal communication, words, body language and mimics. Nonverbal communication is a frequently used method in everyday life relationships. In some cases, people do not express or bring true emotions and thoughts. There may be difference between what they say and what they want to say. In this case, non-verbal communication acts as a reliable source in the sense of what someone actually says or wants to say. They try to understand their emotions and feelings through facial expressions and body movements. Written communication; the superiority of written communication is in its nature of having written evidence. Persons can forget oral communication after a certain period of time. For this reason, the importance of written records is great. People have the opportunity to rearrange their messages by keeping an eye on the ideas they have in writing. Written communication is the first form of communication that is most effective in expanding

the communication limitations of people in time and space. The first condition of your activity in written communication is to choose appropriate words and phrases and to combine words and phrases in a way that is customized to the usual people (Gölönü, S., 2010). The necessity of more formalization of communication in business life today has made written communication more important than oral communication.

General listening behaviors for two people who are communicating with each other are as follows: Focus on what the person tells, bodily attitudes indicating interest, interest in talking to the person speaking, face to face, distance and eye contact. Effective response is related to the feedback of the listener. Properly reflecting the words and feelings of the narrator, asking questions, making summaries and reacting with other words are the skills that enable communication to be effective.

Effective listening requires effort and concentration, involves carefully listening and feedback. It is a form of listening that indicates acceptance, demonstrates correct understanding, shows empathy, and encourages openness. In order for this form of listening to be accomplished, it is important that the message is understood and stored correctly, the notion is recognized for the speaker, verbal and nonverbal cues are answered, and the comprehension effort and concentration are presented to the other side (Akvardar, Y., 2005).

Communication is seen as an important step in the professional sense, in the field of sports, as it is in every field. Because in sports communication almost all communication stages (verbal, written, visual) are included. On the other hand, from Bender's point of view "*communication has become a vital part of almost every business*" shows how much the determination of the sport is in place (Bender P. U., 2000).

The sports activities that take place at various dances activities also contribute to social communication and coexistence. In general, it can be said that communication is composed of content and emotion. Content is the essence of the message and emotion is about how you feel about it (Yılmaz I., 2008). Content is usually spoken, while sentiments are non-spoken. Stress-filled competition sports force coaches and athletes to keep content and emotion under control in communication (Kılıçgil, E., 2009). However, coaches and athletes can improve their incompleteness by working and endeavoring. In addition, through body movements involving activities such as sports, dancing, etc., the individual gains not only technical skills, but also learns to recognize and respect the differences of others. In this context, it can be said that sports play an important role in the acceptance of individual differences in terms of better communication (Çamlıyer, H., 2001).

2. Method

2.1 Research Model and Hypotheses

This study was conducted with the aim of investigating the aggressiveness levels of the students of Kocaeli University Sports Science Faculty according to gender, age, department they studied and sports branches they made, using the survey model.

The hypotheses of this research are as follows:

H1: There is a significant difference between the genders and communication skills of the students of Kocaeli University School of Sports Sciences.

H2: There is a significant difference between the ages and communication skills of the students of Kocaeli University School of Sports Sciences.

H3: There is a significant difference between the departments and communication skills of the students of Kocaeli University School of Sports Sciences.

H4: There is a significant difference between the classes and communication skills of the students of Kocaeli University School of Sports Sciences.

H5: There is a significant difference between the level of aggression and the sports performed by the students of Kocaeli University School of Sports Sciences.

2.2 Population and Sampling

The research population constitutes the students who continue their education in the departments of Coaching Education, Sports Management, Recreation and Physical Education and Sports Teaching departments of Kocaeli University Sports Sciences Faculty in 2018-2019 academic years. After explaining the purpose of investigating the questionnaires, 300 students were randomly selected and the questionnaire as distributed to them. However, 30 missing, incorrect, and incorrectly filled surveys were not evaluated. For this reason, the sample of the research consists of a total of 270 students considering this deficiency.

2.3 Collection of Data

Survey papers were used as data collection tools in the survey. The survey used in the research consists of two parts. In the first section, there are questions about determining demographic information. In the second part, "Communication Skills Evaluation Scale" (IBSQ) was applied to university students developed by Korkut (1997). This form, which includes the directive, contains graded options such as "never (1), rarely (2), sometimes (3), often (4) and always (5)". The high score on the scale without the materials on the contrary means that individuals evaluate their communication skills positively. SPSS 21 package program was used to analyze the obtained data. ANOVA and "t" test statistical analysis methods were applied to evaluate the data.

2.4 Analysis of Data

The data were collected and then analyzed with the SPSS 22 packet program. T-Test and Anova Test were used in the analysis of the data.

3. Results

The demographic distributions of the students who participated in the research were examined first and then the analysis was made according to the demographic

characteristics of the students in order to determine the communication skills of the participants.

Table 1: Demographic Findings Related to Survey Participants

Variable		Frequency (n)	Percent (%)
Gender			
	Female	110	40,7
	Male	160	59,3
Age			
	17-20	127	47,0
	21-24	95	35,2
	25 and above	48	17,8
Department			
	Sports Management	62	23,0
	Coaching Training	65	24,1
	Recreation	100	37,0
	Physical Education and Sports Teacher Training	43	15,9
Class			
	1. Class	91	33,7
	2. Class	82	30,4
	3. Class	81	30,0
	4. Class	16	5,9
Section			
	Individual Sports	99	36,7
	Team Sports	171	63,3
	Total	270	100

Table 1 shows the distributions of gender, age, department, students' class and sport branch variables according to demographic variables of the participating students.

When we look at the demographic characteristics, 110 of the students who participated in the study are female and 60 of them are male students. Of the students who completed the survey, 127 were in the age range of 17-21 years and 95 were in the 21-24 age range, 48 students are between 25 and over. When looking at the distribution of the department, 62 students are studying in Sports Management, 65 Coaching Education, 100 Recreation and 43 students in Physical Education and Sports Teaching. Most of the research is made by the first grade students, even if we look at the classes they have read. 91 First-year students, 82 2nd grade, 81 3rd grade and 16 fourth grade students participated in the study. 105 of the students who participated in the study are doing Individual Sports and 164 are doing Team Sports.

Table 2: Results of t Tests According to Gender Variable of Students Attending the Survey

	Gender	N	X	S.S.	f	p
Communication Skills Measurement Scale	Female	110	3,6480	,591	0,158	,020
	Male	160	3,8198	,597		

A statistically significant difference was found between the groups as a result of the independent sample t test analysis conducted to determine whether the relationship between the genders of the students of Physical Education and Sports and communication skills differed. As a matter of fact, the "p" value is less than 0.05. The average score of male students is higher than that of female students.

For this reason, we accept the hypothesis that there is a significant difference between the genders and communication skills of the students of Physical Education and Sports.

Table 3: Results of One-Way ANOVA for Age Groups of Surveyed Students

	Age	N	X	S.S.	f	p
Communication Skills Measurement Scale	17-20	127	3,710	,524	0,571	,566
	21-24	95	3,797	,660		
	25 and above	48	3,758	,662		

One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), performed to determine whether the communication skills scale differed in terms of age groups of students, was not statistically significant among the groups. Thus, the "p" value is greater than 0.05.

For this reason, the hypothesis that there is a significant difference between the ages and communication skills of the students of the School of Physical Education and Sports is rejected.

Table 4: One-way ANOVA Results According to the Departments of the Participants of the Survey

	Department	N	X	S.S.	f	p
Communication Skills Measurement Scale	Sports Management	62	3,672	,615	1,074	,360
	Coaching Training	65	3,754	,648		
	Recreation	100	3,825	,546		
	Physical Education and Sports Teacher Training	43	3,679	,616		

There was no statistically significant difference between the groups as a result of the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) performed with the aim of determining whether the communication skills scale differed in terms of the departments of the students. Thus, the "p" value is greater than 0.05. In this context, the students of Physical Education and Sports College may have no influence on the communication skills with respect to the departments they have studied.

The hypothesis that there is a significant difference between the departments and communication skills of students of Physical Education and Sports, which we have established before, is rejected.

Table 5: Results of One-Way ANOVA Analysis According to the Classes Studied by the Surveying Students

	Class	N	X	S.S.	f	p	Significant difference
Communication Skills Measurement Scale	1. Class	91	3,779	,601	3,292	,021	(2. Class) – (3. Class)
	2. Class	82	3,594	,659			
	3. Class	81	3,880	,515			
	4. Class	16	3,712	,526			

A statistically significant difference was found between the groups as a result of the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) performed with the aim of determining whether the communication skills scale differed in terms of the classes in which the students studied. Thus the "p" value is less than 0.05. In this context, the classes that the students of Physical Education and Sports College learn may have no effect on their communication skills. Table 3 shows that the communication skills scores of the 3rd grade students are high.

In this context, we accept a hypothesis, that we have already established, that there is a significant difference between the communication skills and the classes of the students of the College of Physical Education and Sports.

Table 6: Results of the t-Test According to the Branch Variable of the Survey Participants

	Branch	N	X	S.S.	f	p
Communication Skills Measurement Scale	Individual Sport	99	3,802	,583	0,410	,268
	Team Sport	171	3,719	,608		

There was no statistically significant difference between the groups as a result of the independent sample t test analysis conducted to determine whether the communication skill measurement scale differed in terms of students' branches. Thus the "p" value is greater than 0.05. In this context, there is no difference between the communication skills of students who play individual sports and those who play team sports.

For this reason, we have rejected the hypothesis that there is a meaningful difference between sports branch and communication skills of the students of the Physical Education and Sports College.

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

In this research, it was researched whether communication skills differ according to the demographic characteristics of Kocaeli University Sports Sciences Faculty students. Independent-Samples T test analysis results, which were applied to determine the relationship between students', participating in the study, gender, department and their sports branches with respect to their communication skills, were examined on the basis of significance level P.0.05. One way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to determine the relationship between age, the departments and classes in which they studied, and communication skills. The significance level of P.0.05 is taken as basis.

It is seen that there is a significant difference according to the mean scores of the gender and communication ability scale of the students of Kocaeli University Sports Sciences Faculty compared to p.0.05, level of significance. According to the average score, communication skills of male students are higher than female students. Ulukan found that there was a statistically significant difference in communication skills according to gender variables in favor of female students. They found that the communication skills of female students were higher than male students (2012). This result does not coincide with our research. Girls better perceive communication skills than boys are connected to the process of socialization by Korkut (2005).

There was no significant difference in the mean scores of the communication skills of the students of different age groups compared to the p 0.05, significance level. The fact that the age variable does not make a meaningful difference in the perception of communication skills overlaps with that of Korkut's study (1997). Bozkurt and his colleagues concluded that the age of the students did not affect the communication skills (2003).

In the study of Tepeköylü, it was concluded that there was not a statistically significant difference between the departments that the students read and their communication skills (2007). This result supports our work.

It is seen that Kocaeli School of Sports Sciences students have a meaningful difference according to the mean scores of the communication skills scale with the classes they have studied compared to the p.0.05 level of significance. It is seen that the communication skills of third grade students are high. Pehlivan's study with classroom teacher candidates showed a meaningful difference in favor of the 4th grade between 1st and 4th grade (2005). Tepeköylü has reached the conclusion that the classes of the students are not a significant influence on the communication skills.

Yilmaz and colleagues evaluated the communication skills of the students of the School of Physical Education and Sports and found no significant difference between their classes and their communication skills. These surveys do not overlap with our work.

It is seen that the students who participate in the study do not have an influence on the communication skills with respect to the individual or the team sports they are playing and communication skills are taken into account when looking at the average score they receive. In the literature, there has been no study done with the students of the School of Sports Sciences or the School of Physical Education and Sports, whose findings can be discussed about this topic. In terms of branch variables, it is necessary to replicate studies on the investigation of communication levels

Communication is very important for sports people. It is believed that the athletes' involvement with each other, with their coaches or fans, will increase the success of athletes in team or individual competitions. It is also believed that it may be useful to put lessons and practices in the development of communication skills into training programs. Again, based on research findings, individuals may be encouraged to play sports to enhance their communication skills. The sport has inherent and

reciprocal communication. Today, the progress of technology is moving individuals away from each other. Any kind of sporting event and organization can help to improve the communication of individuals.

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